

I Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Monthly detection counts of individual hummingbirds and monthly tagging effort at two sites in California, USA. Fill colours indicate Anna’s (ANHU; *C. anna*), Allen’s (ALHU; *S. sasin*), and black-chinned hummingbirds (BCHU; *A. alexandri*). Black-chinned hummingbirds were not captured or tagged at our southern site, while Allen’s Hummingbirds were not captured or tagged at our northern site. RFID tagging of black-chinned hummingbirds commenced in 2019. Red rug plot indicates the number of days spent tagging each month (effort).

II Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Multistate open robust-design with state-uncertainty (MSORD-SU) candidate models and selection criteria. The MSORD-SU model includes parameters for annual survival (S), probability of adopting a migrant strategy over resident strategy in consecutive years (Ψ), proportional composition of migrants and residents on an annual basis (ω), probability of detection (ρ), probability of entering the population between consecutive months (β), and the probability of persisting on the study area between consecutive months (Φ ; constrained to 1 for resident birds). Additionally, the MSORD-SU includes parameters for probability of correctly identifying the migratory strategy of a bird upon detection (δ ; constrained to 1 for resident birds detected from November to January; constrained to 0 for all other detections at all other times) and the probability of being in each state, conditioned on the state being unknown (π ; modelled as a constant). The top candidate model with k estimated terms and the highest Akaike weight was selected and reported.

Parameterization	k	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	Weight	Deviance
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species)· ω (Site + Species) · ρ (Site + Species + stratum)· β (Site:Species:stratum:quad) · Φ (Site + Species * quad + tsatrend)	28	6799.4	0.0	1.0	6743.1
S (Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species)· ω (Site + Species) · ρ (Site + Species + stratum)· β (Site:Species:stratum:quad) · Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend + quad)	26	6822.5	23.0	0.0	6770.2
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Species + stratum)· ω (Site + Species) · ρ (Site + Species + stratum)· β (Site:Species:stratum:quad) · Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	26	6896.9	97.4	0.0	6844.6
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + stratum)· β (Site:Species:stratum:quad) · Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	26	6897.7	98.2	0.0	6845.4
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (stratum)· β (Site:Species:stratum:quad) · Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	25	6897.8	98.3	0.0	6847.5
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + Species + stratum) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	27	6898.5	99.1	0.0	6844.2
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Species) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + Species + stratum) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	25	6902.6	103.2	0.0	6852.3
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + Species + stratum) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	26	6903.8	104.4	0.0	6851.5
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (1) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	24	6908.3	108.9	0.0	6860.1
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + Species + stratum) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	25	6908.9	109.4	0.0	6858.6
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Species) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	25	6909.0	109.6	0.0	6858.7
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	25	6909.3	109.9	0.0	6859.1
S (Site + Species + stratum)· Ψ (Site + Species + stratum) · ω (Site + Species)· ρ (Site + Species) · β (Site:Species:stratum:quad)· Φ (Site + Species + tsatrend)	26	6910.7	111.3	0.0	6858.4
S (1)· Ψ (1)· ω (1)· ρ (1)· β (1)· Φ (1)	7	7597.4	798.0	0.0	7583.4